

**ISLAMIC PRIMARY SCHOOLS IN THE NETHERLANDS:
THE PUPILS' ACHIEVEMENT LEVELS, BEHAVIOUR AND
ATTITUDES AND THEIR PARENTS' CULTURAL BACKGROUNDS***

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History of Islamic Education

Muslims in Western Europe

After the Second World War, sizeable groups of immigrants came to Western Europe. They can be roughly divided into three categories: immigrants from former colonies, foreign workers and refugees. These groups not only imported new languages and cultures, they also brought in different religions. Islam is by far the largest religion, in this respect. Shadid & Van Koningsveld (1996a) estimate that at the moment, some 7 to 10 million European Community residents have an Islamic background. In recent decades, numerous Islamic institutions have been set up. Examples include mosques, the practice of circumcision, Islamic religious instruction, cemeteries and butchers (Shadid & Van Koningsveld, 1991). Rath, Groenendijk & Penninx (1991) hold that two independent factors play a role in this process of institutionalisation, namely political decision-making, which ultimately leads to specific legislation and rules, and ideological assumptions with regard to the position of Muslims in the new country. The process of institutionalisation is highly diversified as a result of major differences in the current, historically informed situation in the various Western European countries, and of the fact that the Muslim community itself is divided and there are differences in the extent to which its various parts are organised and take initiative.

In this article I will be focusing on one of these Islamic institutions, namely the Islamic schools subsidized by the government. In various Western European countries, steps have been taken to found Islamic schools. They have only had a very limited amount of success.¹ In the rest of this section I will concentrate on the Islamic schools in the Netherlands. I will devote attention to how they have come about, their objectives, and the problems they have encountered and still encounter. In addition, I will examine why the initiatives have been successful in the Netherlands but not in the UK and Belgium.

The founding of Islamic schools in the Netherlands and Western Europe

Since the 1988/89 school year, 29 Islamic primary schools have been founded in the Netherlands, where there are a total of approximately 7,300 primary schools. These schools are attended by about 4,000 pupils, largely of Moroccan and Turkish descent. According to Shadid & Van Koningsveld (1992a), this means that less than 4% of the children with an Islamic background actually attend an Islamic primary school.

Not everyone is convinced of the desirability of special Islamic schools; it is not only non-Muslims who disagree on this, but Muslims as well (Teunissen, 1990). Arguments in favour of Islamic schools refer to the dissatisfaction with the existing schools, the improvement of parental participation, the contribution towards the development of the pupils' sense of identity, and the emancipation of the target group (Aarsen & Jansma, 1993; Karagül, 1994; Landman, 1992; Meyer, 1993). Shadid & Van Koningsveld (1992a; 1992b) summarize the objectives as follows: (1) to strengthen the pupils' sense of identity, i.e. cultural and religious personality development in the spirit of Islam; (2) to improve the quality of education, i.e. the achievement levels. The opponents of separate Islamic schools fear however that they will lead to isolation and segregation instead of integration, that no real justice is done to the Dutch norms and values, that they are purely nationality schools, and that they will result in an exodus from the existing schools (Meyer, 1993; Teunissen, 1990). Kabdan (1992) adds that the founding of Islamic schools is more an ideological and political affair than a religious one. In particular, he feels the traditional fundamentalist groups would make use of them. Research by Shadid & Van Koningsveld (1992a; 1992b) seems to support this point of view to some extent. Of the 20 schools that existed in 1991/92, they characterised three as 'liberal' and the remaining 17 as 'orthodox'. The first group were thought to be largely focused on Dutch society, the second on Islamic society (cf. Alkan, 1996; Canatan, 1993a; 1993b; Landman, 1992).

Despite the objections, a legal standpoint was adopted at the policy level: according to the Constitution, every religious group in the Netherlands has the formal right to found a denominational school. However, the people who take the initiative generally do not get a great deal of cooperation from the central or local authorities; sometimes they even feel the authorities have a policy of actively discouraging the founding of Islamic schools (cf. Teunissen, 1990).

It is not entirely clear how and to what extent Islamic schools differ from other schools. According to the central government, schools have to meet certain statutory requirements regarding a minimum number of pupils, the language of instruction has to be Dutch, the teachers have to be qualified and the curriculum has to comply with the stipulations laid down in the Primary Education Act. Research by Shadid & Van Koningsveld (1992a; 1992b) shows that there are a

number of differences as regards the pupil population, the composition of the school board, and the statutes (e.g. the interpretation of Islam, the policy on religious instruction, the observance of Islamic codes of behaviour by teachers and pupils). The special nature of the schools is expressed in the fact that religious instruction is given 1 to 3 hours a week, and generally not in Dutch. The children also have 2.5 hours of Minority Language and Culture Teaching (MLCT) a week during school hours. The way the material is taught and its content seem to depend largely on the position of the school on the liberal – orthodox continuum (cf. Lammers, 1993). At a number of schools the material is tested for compatibility with Islamic norms, the boys are separated from the girls, there are specific behavioural and clothing regulations, and there is space for prayer (Alkan, 1996; Canatan, 1993a). The general impression is that the more liberal schools barely differ if at all from non-Islamic schools (Aarsen & Jansma, 1992).

Due to the lack of sufficient qualified Islamic teachers, more than 70% of the teachers do not have an Islamic background and only speak Dutch. This makes it difficult to convey Islamic norms and values. Another problem is that the parents at the various schools and even within one and the same school tend to have very different viewpoints and expectations, which is a result of their diverse backgrounds (Alkan, 1996). This makes it extremely difficult for the teachers to opt for a certain direction. According to Aarsen & Jansma (1992), many of the teachers, and certainly the non-Muslims, make little effort to do so. This might be one of the reasons why parental participation leaves so much to be desired and the teachers are not serving as bridges. Another reason for the poor parental participation is no doubt that most of the parents have little or no education, no adequate command of the Dutch language, and not enough insight into how the Dutch school system works. This takes us to an important aspect of Islamic education, i.e. that it has largely been a result of the efforts of a small number of religious or political leaders, agents and representatives, and it still remains to be seen just how involved the parents were in founding the schools and choosing the curriculum (cf. Kabdan, 1992; 1993).

Although I have taken the Netherlands as a case, the literature shows that the same largely holds true for countries like Belgium and the UK (e.g. Van Esch & Roovers, 1987; Karagül, 1994; Leman & Renaerts, 1996; Wagtendonk, 1991). Only the outcome is different: there is only one Islamic school in Belgium and none in the UK. How can this be accounted for? Dwyer & Meyer (1996) present an analysis of the backgrounds. In the Netherlands, freedom of education, as is laid down in the Constitution, is expressed in virtually all the facets of the school system. The freedom to found schools, to organise them and to determine the principles they are based on is the reason for the wide variety of schools in the Netherlands. There are two main categories, namely state and denominational schools (e.g. Roman Catholic, Protestant). Under the terms of the Constitution,

all the schools are funded on an equal basis. This means that the facilities provided for Christians cannot be denied to Muslims. As long as a number of conditions have been met, every school is basically entitled to full government funding. The legislation is fairly specific and explicit, making it hard for the local authorities to prevent the founding of these schools. The Islamic schools could also be seen as a kind of compromise. In the Netherlands, as a result of all kinds of legislation, there are hardly any opportunities for children to receive Islamic religious instruction at school (Van Esch & Roovers, 1987).²

In Belgium, Islam was formally recognized as a religion in 1974. Although as a result, Islam theoretically has the same status as Catholicism and Protestantism, this does not automatically mean it is treated the same way in all respects (Leman & Renaerts, 1996). This does not alter the fact that it became possible to organise Islamic religious instruction at state schools on a large scale. According to Dwyer & Meyer (1996), this is probably why there is somewhat less of a demand for separate Islamic schools in Belgium than in the Netherlands. This also has an effect on the political climate. The Muslim community feels that its religious needs are being sufficiently met via religious instruction and that it is not necessary to found separate schools (Wagtendonk, 1991).

In the United Kingdom, however, Islam is not officially recognized and there is not the same freedom of education. As a result, the Muslims in the UK are in a weaker legal position than in the Netherlands and Belgium. There are nevertheless ways to found Islamic schools. According to Wagtendonk (1991), the Muslim community does not see much of a need for this if public funding does not cover 100 per cent of the costs. Dwyer & Meyer (1996) suspect that the ideological role of the established Church is the most important obstacle to Islamic schools. They have the impression that for parents who really want it and who have the financial resources, there is the alternative of the 30 private Islamic schools. The other alternative, Islamic religious instruction, does not appear to have top priority among the Muslims in the UK.

Research into Islamic Schools in the Netherlands

Although there have been Islamic schools in the Netherlands for almost ten years now, very little empirical research has focused on them. It generally either involves case-studies (Aarsen & Jansma, 1992; Meyer, 1993), or specific aspects such as ideology and administrative design (Lammers, 1993; Shadid & Van Koningsveld, 1992a). No large-scale quantitative evaluative studies have been carried out, and no research has been done on the effects and success of the Dutch Islamic schools. Shadid & Van Koningsveld (1992a) refer in this context to the study carried out by the Education Inspectorate, which expects a higher transfer rate to secondary schools. However, this expectation is based on impressions, not on hard facts.

As to the success of the Islamic schools, it is not just empirical data that are

missing, but also information on the backgrounds of the pupils and their parents. No matter how active the parents might be in Islamic education, they only play a minor role in what little literature there is on this subject. In addition, there is every reason to believe parents only play a marginal role in the day-to-day running of the schools and are overshadowed by their agents.

Extensive quantitative information has recently become available via a national cohort study on about half the Islamic schools in the Netherlands. These data pertain in part to the functioning of the pupils and the backgrounds of their parents. Below I will give a description of two studies. In the first study, attention is devoted to some behavioural and attitudinal aspects of the pupils and their school achievement levels. The second study examines a large number of characteristics relating to the pupils' families. Both studies compare Islamic schools, schools with a similar socio-ethnic population, and schools from a representative sample. I round off this article with a summary and conclusions.

Study 1: School Achievement Levels, Behaviour and Attitudes of Pupils

Research Objectives

What is lacking are quantitative data on the quality of Islamic schools. By 'quality' I mean success in terms of achievement levels. This links up with one of the most important points in the debate on the Islamic schools, which is whether or not they are actually able to generate better achievement levels among their pupils than comparable schools.

Data have recently become available that give an impression of the quality of Islamic primary education. Within the framework of the Primary Education cohort study ('PRIMA'), numerous data were collected on pupils, their parents, teachers and schools. These data not only provide insight into the performance of the pupils, but also into their behavioural, attitudinal and family characteristics. These data can be compared for different categories of schools.

Using these data, I would like to address the following questions:

1. What are the achievement levels and behavioural and attitudinal characteristics of pupils at the Islamic schools?
2. How do they differ from pupils at non-Islamic schools?

When I use the term 'achievement levels' I do not just mean test results, but also the teachers' opinions on the cognitive characteristics of the pupils. 'Behavioural and attitudinal characteristics' should be interpreted in terms of the non-cognitive characteristics of the pupils (i.e. behavioural, attitudinal, socio-emotional aspects) and socio-ethnic characteristics of the pupils' families. By 'non-Islamic schools' I mean schools with a similar socio-ethnic pupil population and schools from a nationally representative sample.

Data and Sample

The data for this study are from the PRIMA cohort study. It is a longitudinal study with data collected at primary schools³ once every two years from the school management team and teachers, and the pupils and their parents. The study was started in the 1994/95 school year at almost 700 primary schools, i.e. about 10% of all the Dutch primary schools. In that year, language and arithmetic tests were given to a total of approximately 70,000 pupils in the 2nd, 4th, 6th and 8th forms (5/6-year-olds to 11/12-year-olds) and their teachers supplied information on a number of cognitive and non-cognitive characteristics. In addition, the parents of the pupils in the 4th form completed an extensive questionnaire about the home situation (cf. Jungbluth, Van Langen, Peetsma & Vierke, 1996).

Fifteen Islamic schools take part in PRIMA, which is about half the Islamic schools in the Netherlands. Below the pupils at these schools are compared with pupils at two other categories of schools, i.e. a comparable category and a reference category. The socio-ethnic composition of the schools serves as a criterion for compiling the category of comparable schools. In concrete terms, this means the socio-ethnic composition of the pupil population at schools in this category is similar to the socio-ethnic population at the Islamic schools. The Ministry of Education 'school score' is used to check this. Every primary school in the Netherlands has a school score, which indicates the degree of its socio-ethnic disadvantage. I opted for this criterion because the disadvantaged position of Muslim children has been an important reason for founding separate Islamic schools. The score is based on a combination of the educational and occupational levels of the pupils' parents and their ethnic origins (cf. Driessen & Dekkers, 1997).

On the basis of quantitative analyses, in addition to the 15 participating Islamic schools, I identified 19 non-Islamic schools with the same mean school score. In order to establish to what extent the Islamic schools taking part in PRIMA are representative of the total number of Islamic schools, I compared these 15 Islamic schools with the other 14 Islamic schools that are not taking part. The score was the same for both groups (for more detailed information see Driessen, 1996a). It is consequently possible to conclude that the socio-ethnic composition does not differ in terms of the school score between the Islamic and the comparable schools in the PRIMA sample, nor does it deviate from the socio-ethnic composition of the remaining Islamic schools. Within the total PRIMA sample of 692 schools, it is possible to distinguish a representative part consisting of 416 schools. I use this representative part as a reference category in the analyses. These schools have a total of 35,029 pupils in the 2nd, 4th, 6th and 8th form; the group of Islamic schools has 1,215 pupils and the comparable group 1,828 pupils in the 2nd, 4th, 6th and 8th form.

Instrumentation

For this first part of the study, three of the PRIMA instruments are of importance: the class form, the pupil profile and the performance tests.

With the aid of the *class form*, information was collected at the schools relating to the pupils' gender, age, and socio-ethnic background.

The *pupil profile* is made up of some 40 statements. The teachers are asked to indicate to what extent they are applicable to their pupils. These statements have been reduced to a limited number of cognitive and non-cognitive factors by means of a scale analysis (cf. Driessen & Haanstra, 1996a). The cognitive factors include:

- under-achievement: 'the pupil could really do better'
- pupil at risk of failure: 'this pupil requires professional help at school'
- secondary school prognosis: the school type the pupil is likely to go to after primary school.

The non-cognitive factors, i.e. the behavioural and attitudinal characteristics, include:

- well-being: 'the pupil feels at ease with the teacher'
- self-confidence: 'the pupil is confident, sure of himself'
- social behaviour: 'the pupil never has fights'
- attitude towards work: 'the pupil works with great accuracy'
- health: 'the pupil gets enough exercise'
- parental support: 'the parents show a great deal of interest in reading and general education'.

The scores on these characteristics range from 1 to 5; they have been calculated in such a way that the higher the score, the more the characteristic applies to the pupil. Since unlike the other characteristics, 'under-achievement' and 'pupil at risk of failure' are in fact negative attributes, a high score on these two points is of course unfavourable.

With regard to the cognitive characteristics, two *performance tests* were also administered to each form. In the 2nd form these were Concepts ('Begrippen') and Structuring ('Ordenen'). These multiple choice tests are made up of 60 and 42 items. They give an indication of the pre-reading and pre-arithmetic level. In the 4th, 6th and 8th form, language and arithmetic tests were administered to show the overall language and arithmetic proficiency level. They also always consist of approximately 60 and 40 items. Since there are four different tests per subject area, the scores cannot simply be compared over the forms. In order to make this possible, the test scores were put on a scale by means of a calibration procedure, making it possible to draw a direct comparison of the scores from the four forms in the subject areas of language and arithmetic.

As far as the response to the research instruments is concerned, I would like to make the following comment. The test results are available for almost all the pupils, but this is not always the case for the other data. Non-response analyses

indicate that the mean scores of the reference category on the pupil profile scores show a slight over-estimation of the actual mean scores. For more information on these instruments and characteristics, I refer the reader to Driessen & Haanstra (1996a) and Jungbluth, Van Langen, Peetsma & Vierke (1996).

Results

First of all, I would like to say something about the background characteristics of the pupils. In each of the forms, there is a higher percentage of boys at the Islamic schools than at the comparable schools or reference schools. These differences are however not statistically significant. As to age, there are small differences: the pupils at the comparable schools are generally a little older than at the Islamic and reference schools. As far as socio-ethnic background is concerned, there are no differences between the Islamic and the comparable schools. This is of course hardly surprising, as the two groups of schools were matched for this type of characteristic. There are however some major differences with the reference schools. To give an impression of these differences, I calculated the percentage of immigrant children of parents with a low educational and occupational level for all of the forms together. For the Islamic schools, it is 98%, for the comparable schools 96% and for the reference schools 11%.

In Table 1, I present the scores on the cognitive and non-cognitive characteristics. The first two columns show the mean scores for the pupils at the Islamic schools and at schools in the comparable group. The third column shows to what extent there is a significant and/or relevant difference between the two groups. The asterisk shows whether or not a difference is significant at a 5% level. The Eta^2 value subsequently shows whether or not the difference is relevant; the percentage of variance accounted for is obtained by multiplying this value by 100. The relevance criterion is often set at 2%, which means one can only speak of a relevant difference if at least 2% variance is explained. To give a better idea of where to place the scores for the two above-mentioned groups, in the fourth and fifth column I also show the mean scores and standard deviations for the pupils in the reference sample. With all these data, it is not only possible to draw a comparison at any given moment, in this case in one particular form, but also – and this is interesting with regard to the language and arithmetic achievement levels – to see if there is any development in the mean scores of the more advanced forms.

As regards the first six non-cognitive factors, the pupils at the Islamic schools – measured by the opinions of their teachers – generally always do slightly better than those at comparable schools. In some cases these differences are significant and relevant, although they are not very consistent over the forms. The pupils are sometimes a little more self-confident, a little more sociable, have a somewhat better attitude towards work, are healthier and get a little more parental

Table 1: Cognitive and non-cognitive pupil characteristics, 2nd, 4th, 6th and 8th forms (means)

		Islamic schools	comparable schools	Eta ²	reference schools	sd
<i>2nd Form</i>	– well being	4.0	4.1	.00	4.1	.5
	self-confidence	3.6	3.4	.02*	3.6	.7
	social behaviour	3.5	3.4	.00	3.6	.7
	attitude about work	3.5	3.3	.02*	3.5	.7
	health	3.8	3.4	.11*	3.8	.6
	home climate	3.4	3.1	.03*	4.0	.8
	– under-achievement	2.8	3.0	.01*	2.5	.8
	pupil at risk	2.5	2.7	.01*	2.2	.8
	prognosis sec. school	2.8	2.7	.00	2.9	.9
	– language	933	941	.02*	969	35
	arithmetic	840	869	.07*	889	66
<i>4th Form</i>	– well-being	4.0	4.0	.00	4.0	.5
	self-confidence	3.5	3.4	.00	3.5	.7
	social behaviour	3.6	3.4	.01*	3.6	.7
	attitude about work	3.5	3.4	.00	3.5	.7
	health	3.5	3.3	.02*	3.7	.6
	home climate	3.2	3.0	.01	3.9	.8
	– under-achievement	2.7	2.8	.01*	2.6	.8
	pupil at risk	2.3	2.6	.02*	2.3	.9
	prognosis sec. school	2.6	2.5	.00	2.8	1.2
	– language	986	990	.01*	1030	37
	arithmetic	1000	1001	.00	1041	67
<i>6th Form</i>	– well-being	4.1	4.0	.00	4.0	.6
	self-confidence	3.7	3.5	.02*	3.5	.7
	social behaviour	3.5	3.6	.01	3.6	.7
	attitude about work	3.5	3.5	.00	3.5	.7
	health	3.7	3.6	.00	3.7	.6
	home climate	3.4	3.1	.03*	3.8	.8
	– under-achievement	3.0	2.9	.00	2.6	.9
	pupil at risk	2.1	2.3	.01	2.2	.9
	prognosis sec. school	2.7	2.0	.08*	2.7	1.3
	– language	1034	1034	.00	1071	34
	arithmetic	1112	1104	.01*	1133	41
<i>8th Form</i>	– well-being	4.0	3.9	.00	3.9	.6
	self-confidence	3.7	3.6	.00	3.5	.7
	social behaviour	3.7	3.6	.00	3.6	.7
	attitude about work	3.5	3.4	.00	3.4	.8
	health	3.7	3.6	.01*	3.7	.6
	home climate	3.3	3.3	.00	3.8	.8
	– under-achievement	3.0	2.8	.01	2.7	.9
	pupil at risk	2.3	2.4	.01	2.2	.9
	– language	1077	1078	.00	1117	38
	arithmetic	1175	1163	.02*	1196	47

* p < .05

support when it comes to matters related to school. The difference in terms of health in the 2nd form is particularly striking: the pupils eat better, sleep more, get more exercise and do not get tired quite as quickly. The differences between the Islamic and the reference schools are generally also very small. There is however one exception: pupils at the Islamic schools generally receive less parental support.

I would like to turn to the next three non-cognitive factors. There is a slightly more positive outlook on 'under-achievement' at the Islamic schools in the 2nd and 4th form than at the comparable schools (a low score is more positive here than a high one). As to 'pupils at risk of failure', this applies to all the forms and the teachers at the Islamic schools are slightly more optimistic in their secondary school prognosis. However, the pupils at the reference schools are nearly always given a more favourable assessment than the ones at the Islamic schools.

Lastly, I would like to examine the test results of the pupils. At the Islamic schools, the achievement levels in language in the 2nd and 4th form are slightly lower than at the comparable schools; in the 6th and 8th form these achievement levels are the same. As regards arithmetic, however, the difference in the 2nd form is considerably higher (7% variance accounted for) and unfavourable for the Islamic schools, in the 4th form there is no difference, and in the 6th and 8th form the Islamic schools are actually better. As was to be expected, the differences between the Islamic schools and the reference category are large: in terms of language always approximately a full standard deviation, and in terms of arithmetic a half to three-quarters of a standard deviation.

When one speaks of 'educational outcomes' one generally means achievement levels, and they are what is often given the most attention. Compare for example the objectives in the statutes of the Islamic schools: the aim is to improve the achievement levels. This is why I want to examine this for a moment. One important question is how the achievement levels of the pupils at the Islamic and the comparable schools develop in relation to those of the pupils in the reference group. As far as their 'development' is concerned, it is essential to specify what it entails. Strictly speaking, the research at hand is still not a longitudinal study. We do not constantly monitor the same pupils in various years. Up until now, there has only been one measuring moment. We do however compare pupils in various forms; this involves different pupils. What we therefore compare are the mean achievement levels of pupils in ascending forms at three categories of schools. The comparison is not so much at the pupil level but at the level of the forms. From this point of view, I then carry out two kinds of analyses. First I look at the amount of progress made between the forms and compare this per school category; then I determine the relative progress at the Islamic and the comparable schools in relation to the reference schools.

The top part of Table 2 shows the results of the initial analyses. Here the score in the 2nd form for language and arithmetic per school category is subtracted from the score in the 4th form, in the 4th form from the 6th, and in the 6th form from the 8th. The bottom line shows the overall progress: from the 2nd form to the 8th. In these comparisons, one should bear in mind that the achievement levels can only be compared within each of the two subjects (language and arithmetic) and not with each other. In the bottom part of the table, I subsequently present the differences between the Islamic and the comparable schools and the reference schools. To this end, the score of the Islamic and the comparable schools per form has been subtracted from the score in the reference category and subsequently divided by the accompanying standard deviation. The result (the Effect Size) gives an impression of the relative difference between the two categories of schools.

Table 2: 'Development' of language and arithmetic achievement levels per school category and in relation to the reference group (means)

class	Islamic schools	language comparable schools	reference schools	Islamic schools	arithmetic comparable schools	reference schools
2 →4	53	49	61	160	132	152
4 →6	48	44	41	112	103	92
6 →8	43	44	46	63	59	63
2 →8	144	137	148	335	294	307
2	1.03	.57		.74	.30	
4	1.19	1.08		.61	.60	
6	1.09	1.08		.51	.71	
8	1.05	1.03		.45	.70	

As far as language is concerned, there is a difference at the top part of Table 2 of 53 points between the 4th and 2nd form at the Islamic schools; in the comparable group the difference is only 49 points, and in the reference category it is no less than 61 points. In total the difference between the 2th and 8th form at the Islamic schools is 144 points; at the comparable schools it is slightly less and at the reference schools slightly more. The situation is somewhat different for arithmetic. The Islamic schools go through the strongest development as a group, and they develop even more than the reference schools. If one assumes that individual pupils undergo a constant development as they go through primary school, this is an indication that as far as arithmetic is concerned, pupils at the Islamic schools catch up more quickly than at the comparable schools. In absolute terms, however, they still lag very much behind the pupils in the

reference category, as is illustrated by the bottom part of Table 2. Here, per form, the relative difference as compared to the reference category is expressed in terms of standard deviations. To give an impression of how the differences are interpreted, a standard deviation of .2 is often seen as small, one of .5 as moderate, one of .8 as large and one of 1 as very large. When it comes to language, the difference at the Islamic schools as compared to the reference category is very large and remains that way over the forms. For the comparable schools, there is a moderate difference in the 2nd form, but in the other forms it is at about the same level as at the Islamic schools. For arithmetic, another pattern emerges. At the Islamic schools the difference gets smaller further on, while at the comparable schools it gets larger – which is in line with what was concluded on the basis of the top part of the table.

Study 2: Cultural Backgrounds of the Parents

Research Objectives

In addition to there hardly being any empirical data on the performance of the pupils at Islamic schools, very little is known about the backgrounds of the pupils and their parents. Within the framework of the PRIMA cohort, more extensive quantitative information has now become available about the family backgrounds of pupils at Islamic schools. The objective of this study is to gain some insight into the backgrounds of the pupils at Islamic schools: the conditions they grow up in, the socio-ethnic background of their parents, the cultural, linguistic, religious and socialising influences they are confronted with at home. As in Study 1, in this exploratory study I do not simply describe the pupils at the Islamic schools, I also compare their situation with those of pupils at non-Islamic schools with a similar socio-ethnic pupil population and at a nationally representative sample of schools.

Data and Sample

Like the data for Study 1, the data for this second study have come from the PRIMA cohort study. Data on test results and behavioural and attitudinal characteristics were collected for all the forms; in addition, for one form, namely the 4th form, the parents of the pupils were asked to complete an extensive questionnaire about themselves, their children and their home situation. I will discuss the data from this questionnaire below.

Of the 15 Islamic schools participating in PRIMA, 13 returned the data on the parents. I will compare this group of Islamic schools with a comparable group and a reference group, which were selected in the same way as in the first study. The comparable group consists of 14 schools and the reference group of 416 schools. Analyses showed that as regards the socio-ethnic composition of the population, the Islamic schools do not differ from the remaining Islamic schools

in the PRIMA sample, nor do they deviate from the remaining Islamic schools in the entire group of primary schools.

The data I report on below have been collected by means of a written questionnaire completed by the parents of the pupils. The response to this kind of research instrument can be problematic, in particular if it involves immigrant parents. At the 13 Islamic schools, 347 pupils were in the 4th form; at the 14 schools in the comparable group, there were 409 pupils in the 4th form. There is a great difference in the response to the parent questionnaires between the two groups: 48 and 41%. In the reference category there were 9671 pupils, and a parent response of 75%.

To get an impression of possible selectivity as a result of non-response, I carried out two kinds of analyses. I checked to see if the differences in response between the three school categories depended on the social background of the parents, and found that only within the reference schools was there a difference: the parents with a lower educational level failed to return the questionnaire slightly more often than the parents with a higher educational level. In addition, I checked to see whether the language and arithmetic achievement levels of the pupils with and without parent data differed in any way. Here too, there were no differences within the Islamic and comparable schools, but there did appear to be differences within the reference schools. Pupils without parent data did somewhat more poorly than pupils with those data (for more details, see Driessen, 1996b). Although we have to be careful with this, the latter might indicate that part of the data show a picture that is perhaps a little too favourable. As a result of the non-response, the numbers of pupils with parent data are spread over the three school categories in the following way: the 13 Islamic schools account for 167 pupils, the 14 comparable schools for 166 pupils and the 400 reference schools for 7284 pupils.

Instrumentation

Within the parent questionnaire, it is possible to distinguish four groups of characteristics.

- *Family structure characteristics*: number of children, one or two parent family, and for both parents their dates of birth, country of birth, length of stay in the Netherlands, nationality, education, occupation and income.
- *Family cultural characteristics*: self-attribution of the language and cultural community of the mother, father and child, and in addition the command of Dutch of both parents, satisfaction with life and feelings of empowerment, reading behaviour.
- *Pedagogical climate characteristics*: the importance attached to religion in the upbringing, importance attached to learning the parents' mother tongue, the importance of traditional, school-adapted behaviour, the importance of

independent, critical behaviour, talking with the child, attending parent meetings at school, talking with the teachers, satisfaction with the school.

- *Pupil characteristics*: gender, country of birth, length of stay in the Netherlands, informal spoken language, sleeping habits, frequency of reading and watching TV, pre-school care, form they were in when they entered primary school, how often they have had to repeat a year, participation and frequency of MLCT and Koran study, frequency of homework, help with homework.

For a technical account of all these characteristics (scale construction and reliability) I refer to Driessen & Haanstra (1996a).

Results

For each of the three school categories, I calculated the mean scores and standard deviations per characteristic. I checked to see if there was a significant difference between the Islamic and the comparable schools and how strong the nominal metric correlation (η) was between attending an Islamic school and the characteristic in question. I started from a significance level of $p < .05$, which generally amounts to a correlation of around .15. The data are shown in Table 3; I have confined myself to characteristics on which the Islamic schools differ significantly from the comparable schools. Wherever applicable, in brackets, the table also shows the range of the scores next to the characteristic concerned. In the description below, to a certain extent I also go into other non-significant differences. When I speak about differences, in principle I always mean differences between the Islamic and the comparable schools. Whenever I refer to differences with the reference schools, I make explicit mention of this.

Family structure characteristics. A total of 8% of the pupils attending Islamic schools and 15% of the pupils at the comparable schools come from one-parent families. The difference is not significant, however. At the reference schools, 6% of the children are from a one-parent family. The pupils at the Islamic and comparable schools are from families with a relatively large number of children, on average 3.5 to 3.9. In the reference category, this figure is considerably lower, i.e. just over 2.5. As far as the age of the parents is concerned, there is hardly any difference between the various school categories. The mothers are around 35 and the fathers around 39 years old. There are also hardly any differences as to the percentage of parents born abroad, at least not in the case of the Islamic and the comparable schools (between 92 and 97%). There is of course a difference in relation to the reference schools; nationally 10% of the parents were born abroad. Closer analysis shows that there are differences in ethnic origin, defined in terms of the parents' specific country of birth. For example, 84% of the mothers of the children attending the Islamic schools were born in Turkey or Morocco, 7% in the Netherlands and the remaining 10% elsewhere. At the comparable schools, the percentages are 61, 8 and 31 (with 14% of Surinamese origin). The fact that

Table 3: Family and pupil characteristics per school category; only $p \leq .05$ (means, standard deviations, correlations)

	Islam.	comp.			ref.	
	means	means	sd	eta	means	sd
<i>Family structure characteristics:</i>						
nationality mother (% foreign)	82	62	45	-.22	5	22
nationality father (% foreign)	78	58	47	-.21	5	22
<i>Family cultural characteristics:</i>						
language and cultural community of child (% foreign)	84	73	41	-.13	5	23
<i>Family pedagogical characteristics:</i>						
importance attached to religion in upbringing (1-4)	3.9	3.4	.7	-.36	2.6	1.0
importance attached to learning parents' language (1-3)	2.8	2.6	.6	-.16	2.6	.7
talking to the teacher (1-3)	2.3	2.1	.8	-.12	2.1	.7
satisfaction about school (1-4)	3.2	3.1	.5	-.14	3.1	.5
<i>Pupil characteristics:</i>						
length of stay in the Netherlands (years)	3.8	5.2	2.3	.30	4.2	2.3
informal language spoken with mother (% foreign)	84	69	43	-.17	5	21
time of getting up on weekdays (time)	7.1	7.3	.4	.20	7.1	.3
watching TV weekdays (1-5)	2.7	3.0	1.1	.13	2.0	.9
watching TV weekend (1-5)	3.8	4.1	1.1	.12	3.1	1.1
pre-school care (% yes)	21	40	46	.21	81	39
repeating a year at primary school (% yes)	19	31	43	.14	14	35
MLCT participation (% yes)	80	52	48	-.30	-	-
Koran classes (% yes)	83	42	48	-.42	3	17
homework frequency (1-3)	2.0	1.6	.6	-.35	1.7	.6

the school score is the same therefore does not mean there are no differences in the ethnic composition of the school populations. There is no significant difference in the length of time the parents have been in the Netherlands. This does not alter the fact that the immigrant parents of the pupils at the reference schools have been in the Netherlands for 2 to 3 years longer than those of the pupils at the comparable schools, who in turn have been here 1 to 2 years longer than those of the pupils at the Islamic schools (with the mean scores for mothers of 12.4 and fathers of 15.8 years). With regard to nationality, there is a large difference of 20%. Parents from the comparable group significantly less frequently have the Dutch nationality. In terms of education, occupation and income the parents of the children at the Islamic and the comparable schools do not differ very much. There are however once again major differences with the reference schools. The parents of the children at the Islamic schools on average stated that the highest level of education they had completed was primary school, while the parents of the children at the reference schools said they had completed the second stage of secondary school or senior vocational school. The income of the parents of

the children at the Islamic schools is between 1500 and 2000 Dutch guilders a month, and that of the parents from the reference group between 3000 and 3500 Dutch guilders a month.

Family cultural characteristics. The children from the group of Islamic schools are more strongly focused on a non-Dutch language and cultural community than the children from the comparable schools; for the mothers and fathers this difference does not play a role. As far as the various aspects of the command of the Dutch language are concerned, there are no differences between the Islamic and the comparable schools. These differences are however once again evident in relation to the reference schools (1 to 2 standard deviations, in particular with respect to the mothers' command of Dutch). The parents were asked a number of questions about the extent to which they were satisfied with their financial situation, their education, their work and living conditions. The parents of the children at the Islamic and the comparable schools score in the middle category; the parents of the children in the reference group clearly score higher, in particular the mothers (1.5 sd higher). The parents were subsequently asked whether they felt they could influence any of these four aspects. The parents in the Islamic and comparable group are not optimistic about the amount of influence they can exert, and the ones in the reference category are a little more hopeful (in particular the mothers: 1.5 sd higher). As regards the reading behaviour, there are no differences on any of the reading aspects for either the mothers or the fathers. Here too, there are relatively major differences between these two groups and the reference group.

Pedagogical climate characteristics. The parents of the children at the Islamic schools attach a great deal of importance to the role religion plays in their children's upbringing (almost the maximum score of 4), more than the parents of the children in the comparable group, and a great deal more than the parents of the children in the reference group. As regards 'the importance of traditional, school-adapted behaviour' and 'the importance of independent, critical behaviour' there are no differences, although there is a difference with the reference group on the first characteristic. In that group, less importance is attached to adapted behaviour. There are no differences as regards talking to the child about reading, watching TV and playing. Strikingly enough, this is done slightly less in the reference group, which can be seen as less favourable. As regards attending parent meetings, report card consultations and talks about the children, there are no real differences, although this is slightly lower than it is in the reference group. At the Islamic schools, the parents tend to talk to the teachers a little bit more frequently than at the comparable schools, but just as frequently as at the reference schools. This does not mean a great deal in itself; after all, parents often only go to talk to the teacher if there are problems. The degree of satisfaction

with the school was determined on the basis of eight statements. The parents of the children at the Islamic schools are more satisfied than the parents of the children at the comparable schools and at the reference schools.

Pupil characteristics. As far as gender is concerned, there are no differences. There are also no differences regarding the country of birth; more than 20% of the pupils were born outside the Netherlands. This is in sharp contrast with the reference group, where only 4% of the pupils were born abroad. It also appeared that the pupils at the Islamic schools who were born elsewhere have been in the Netherlands for a much shorter period of time; the difference is almost eighteen months. This means these children (of which the absolute number is small) on average attend Dutch primary school from the very beginning in the 1st form (which is kindergarten). The questions relating to the informal spoken language were put to all the parents, regardless of their ethnic origin. On the whole, the children attending the Islamic schools more frequently speak a foreign language than the children at the comparable schools. This difference is however only significant for the mothers. These data show a clear generation effect. The children tend to communicate with their mothers in a non-Dutch language quite a lot, and with their fathers a little less, with their siblings considerably less frequently and with their friends even less. The pupils at the Islamic schools get up significantly earlier on weekdays to go to school. Perhaps this has to do with the fact that they travel a longer distance to get to school. They do not however go to bed any earlier. In the weekend, there are no significant differences as regards what time they get up and go to bed. There are also no differences in the number of hours of sleep they get. The pupils at the comparable schools do however watch significantly more TV. The score 2 stands for 1 to 2 hours a day, 3 for 2 to 3 hours a day and 4 for 3 to 4 hours a day. In addition, there is also a major difference in relation to the reference category, which watches even less TV. Although the pupils at the Islamic schools tend to do a little more reading, this difference is not significant. It is striking that they do read a lot more than the pupils in the reference category. Relatively speaking, the pupils at the Islamic schools have not very often attended any form of pre-school care (e.g. day care centre or pre-school play group); a mere 20% has. This is only half of the comparable group, and only a quarter of the reference group. The number of years they attended pre-school care is however the same for all three groups, i.e. around 2 years. If we look at the moment when the pupils started primary school, there are no differences: for both groups it is halfway through the 1st form. This does deviate from the pupils in the reference category, who started about 4 months earlier. As regards having to repeat a year in the first four forms, there are major differences: at the Islamic schools this is less than 20% and at the comparable schools more than 30%. This should be viewed with some caution, since it is not clear at which school the pupils have had to repeat a year. The

pupils at the Islamic schools are more likely to have been to another school first than the pupils at the comparable schools. Probably all the pupils in the 2nd to the 8th form from the first batch attended another school first. There are significant differences when it comes to attending Minority Language and Culture Teaching classes, which are specially designed for immigrants: 80 versus 48%. The number of hours of instruction is virtually the same at both categories of schools. There are also very major differences with regard to attending Koran classes: 83 versus 48%. It is striking however that the number of hours of Koran study the pupils at the comparable schools receive tends to be higher (5.2 versus 3.9, but this difference is not significant). The children at the Islamic schools are more often given homework than the children at the comparable schools or the reference schools; 2 in this context means 'occasionally' and 3 'often'. As regards whatever help the pupils receive with their homework from their parents or siblings, there appear to be no differences. In the reference group, the mothers tend to help their children with their homework more often (1 sd more), and in the two other categories the pupils are considerably more often helped by brothers or sisters (also 1 sd more). This can be explained by the fact that the immigrant mothers have had little education and do not speak enough Dutch to actually help their children, which is why older siblings often take over this task.

To summarize the results presented above, in so far as there are differences between the pupils at the Islamic schools and the comparable schools, they are generally not very large. No more than five correlations come to .30 or more. The maximum correlation amounts to -.42, which pertains to Koran study. Pupils at the Islamic schools more frequently attend Koran classes than pupils at comparable schools. This is logical for two reasons. In the first place, the comparable schools do in fact have the same school score as the Islamic schools, but at the comparable schools there are more pupils from ethnic minorities who are not Muslims. A second reason is that in principle, Koran classes are part of the regular curriculum at the Islamic schools. Perhaps the reason not all the pupils attend Koran classes has to do with the schools having trouble finding qualified Koran teachers (cf. Aarsen & Jansma, 1992) or the pupils getting exemptions from these classes (Shadid & Van Koningsveld, 1992a). It is also clear that the parents of the children at the Islamic schools attach more importance to religion in the upbringing; this was probably one of their main reasons for sending their children to these schools. The fact that pupils at Islamic schools attend MLCT classes more often can probably best be seen as an indication of their parents' stronger orientation towards the country of origin. In addition, the pupils at the Islamic schools are far more frequently given homework. In line with their objectives, this might be part of a specific strategy at these schools to make more of an effort to reduce the educational disadvantage of immigrant children than 'regular' primary schools tend to make.

In order to gain greater insight into the relations between the background characteristics and achievement levels, I have also computed the correlations and carried out two regression analyses using the scores on the language and arithmetic tests as dependent variables. I have selected nine background characteristics specific to immigrant children and their families, which give an indication of the immigrants' family cultural, linguistic and religious orientation towards the Netherlands. These characteristics are (cf. Table 3): the family's nationality (father's plus mother's), the family's cultural orientation (based on the orientation of both the parents plus the child), the importance of learning the parents' language, the family's command of Dutch (the proficiency level of both parents), the informal language spoken with mother, MLCT participation, the importance of religion in the upbringing, attending Koran classes and the variable Islamic schools versus comparable schools. Two of these characteristics more or less indicate an orientation to the Netherlands (parents' command of Dutch and Islamic school), the others indicate an orientation to the immigrant group. The results of these analyses are presented in Table 4. The upper part of the table contains the correlations, the lower part the means, standard deviations and ranges, and the unstandardized regression coefficients (B). For the regression analyses, I use the 'Enter' method, which means all the effects are estimated simultaneously.

It is clear from the upper part of the table that the correlations are generally low. The correlations between attending an Islamic school versus a comparable school and the language and arithmetic test scores are only .10 and .04 and are not significant. The lower part of the table shows four significant coefficients with regard to the language achievement levels. In general the coefficients point in the expected direction, i.e. the more the family is oriented towards the immigrant group, the lower the test scores. There is, however, one exception to this rule, which is that attending Koran classes has a positive effect; I have no explanation for this unexpected finding. The effect of the importance parents attach to religion in their children's upbringing is negative, which means the more importance they attach to religion, the poorer the results. The parents' command of Dutch has a positive influence on the language achievement levels. Children who attend Minority Language and Culture Teaching classes achieve poorer results. Earlier research has shown that this might be related to the fact that these classes are given during school hours, so that the pupils miss part of the regular Dutch curriculum and fall behind as a result (cf. Driessen, 1996c). Whether or not a pupil attends an Islamic school does not exert any influence. In total only 8.1% of the variance in the language achievement levels is explained. This is not very much in itself, as is understandable since we are focusing on Islamic and comparable schools, and a selection already took place beforehand on a number of characteristics that could be relevant in a representative sample. As regards

Table 4: Correlations between the language and arithmetic achievement levels and background characteristics; means, standard deviations and ranges; unstandardized regression coefficients

	nat.	cult.	p.l.	Dutch	i.l.	MLCT	reli.	Koran	Islam.	lang.	arith.
nationality family	1.00										
cultural orientation											
family	.37**	1.00									
importance parents'											
language	.20**	.11	1.00								
parents' command											
of Dutch	-.34**	-.20**	-.03	1.00							
informal language											
with mother	.39**	.27**	.15**	-.41**	1.00						
MLCT participation											
importance attached	.16*	.09	.17**	-.05	.25**	1.00					
to religion											
Koran classes	.31**	.23**	.27**	-.25**	.36**	.23**	1.00				
Islamic school	.26**	.15*	.25**	-.06	.17*	.62**	.37**	1.00			
language achieve-	-.26**	-.09	-.16**	.08	-.17**	-.30**	-.36**	-.42**	1.00		
ment											
arithmetic achieve-	-.15*	-.13*	-.11	.21**	-.23**	-.16*	-.22**	-.00	.10	1.00	
ment											
	-.02	-.04	-.07	.02	.05	-.03	-.04	-.07	.04	.36**	1.00
	m	sd	range	B lang.	B arith.						
language achieve-											
ment	988.36	30.22									
arithmetic achieve-											
ment	1002.65	55.48									
nationality family	1.33	.90	0-2	-.61	-.14						
cultural orientation											
family	2.52	.97	0-3	-1.14	-1.90						
importance parents'											
language	2.68	.55	1-3	-2.92	-5.65						
parents' command											
of Dutch	2.18	.57	1-3	6.25*	3.77						
informal language											
with mother	1.76	.43	1-2	-5.78	12.65						
MLCT participation											
importance attached	1.66	.48	1-2	-10.76*	-.31						
to religion											
Koran classes	3.63	.75	1-4	-5.63*	-1.67						
Islamic school											
Constant	1.65	.48	1-2	11.63*	-4.59						
	1.50	.50	1-2	1.79	2.06						
				1012.83**	1003.23**						

* $p \leq .05$; ** $p \leq .01$ (correlations: two-tailed; regression: one-tailed)

explaining the differences in the arithmetic achievement levels, I can be brief. There is no characteristic that makes a significant contribution. Here, too, it does not really matter whether a pupil attends an Islamic school or not.

Summary and Conclusions

In this article I have described of a number of cognitive and non-cognitive characteristics of pupils at Islamic schools. I compared them with those of pupils

at a group of schools with a similar socio-ethnic population and with those of pupils at a nationally representative reference group of schools. The behavioural and attitudinal characteristic differences between the three categories of schools are generally either very small or non-existent. If there are any differences at all, they are not very stable over the various forms. As far as test results are concerned, there are major differences between the pupils at the reference schools and the other schools. Compared with the pupils at the comparable schools, the pupils at the Islamic schools also tend to do slightly less well in language in the lower forms; they do however do equally well in the higher forms. As far as arithmetic is concerned, they tend to do far more poorly in the lower forms, but better in the highest form. With one exception, in the higher forms the pupils at the Islamic and the comparable schools seem to be just as far behind in language compared with the reference schools. As far as arithmetic is concerned, however, the achievement levels of the pupils at the Islamic schools appear to improve somewhat, whereas those of the pupils at the comparable schools appear to deteriorate.

It is not clear whether the latter differences are realistic developments. We are not talking about longitudinal research data here, with the same pupils monitored as they go through school, but about a cross-sectional comparison of the mean scores for ascending forms at a given moment in time. It is possible that the differences are related to the moment the pupils enter the school. Although the Islamic schools have been in existence for a number of years and have thus been in a reasonable position to develop and enhance their direction and approach, the available data do not show when each of the pupils registered at an Islamic school. Some of the pupils started in the 1st form, and others in a higher form. The positive development in achievement levels at the Islamic schools could consequently be attributed to the quality of education at these schools; it is also possible that pupils who first attended another school and only entered in a higher form make the achievement levels at the Islamic schools higher in the higher forms than at the comparable schools. In that case, the higher level is not an effect of the Islamic schools, but of the schools the pupils initially attended. Whether one can speak of a development, and if so, how it will proceed, can be investigated in due course in greater detail using the PRIMA data collected in the 1996/97 school year.

As regards the non-cognitive data, it is often hard to establish exactly what is the cause and what is the consequence. Do immigrant children feel more at home at Islamic schools because of the specific nature and approach used by these schools? Is the gap between the school and the home environment smaller as a result, and do they have a better attitude about work because of this? Or does it involve a specific group of parents who send their children to Islamic schools, i.e. parents who devote a great deal of attention at home to teaching their children

a good attitude about work? Does this subsequently have a positive effect on the extent to which the children feel at home at school?

It is clear from the analyses that the data on the 2nd form show the greatest number of differences on the non-cognitive aspects – more and larger ones than in the higher forms. For the moment it is still not clear exactly how this result should be interpreted. Is it largely determined by the personality traits of the children themselves, their upbringing at home, or the approach used at the schools? Or is it largely a question of an interaction between these three factors?

Apart from the cognitive and non-cognitive characteristics and test results of the pupils from the 2nd, 4th, 6th and 8th forms, a number of characteristics relating to the home situation of the pupils in the 4th form were examined. They were related to the family structure, family culture and pedagogical climate and to the pupils themselves. The core of the univariate and multivariate analyses consisted of a comparison of more than 80 characteristics of the pupils at the Islamic schools and the schools with a similar socio-ethnic composition. The most important conclusion on the basis of the analyses is that the two groups of pupils hardly differ and in so far as they do, the differences are generally very small. Some of the most important distinguishing characteristics are directly related to the parents choosing the Islamic school. It is possible to cite the relatively great importance they attach to their children attending Koran classes and the role of religion in the upbringing of their children. One characteristic also associated with this choice is related to the fact that probably as a result of the longer travelling time, the children have to get up a little earlier to be at the Islamic school on time. One important distinguishing factor is also that the pupils are more often given homework at the Islamic schools than at the comparable schools. Whether this can be explained as a deliberate strategy on the part of the school to combat educational disadvantages is still not clear.

As regards explaining the differences in the achievement levels of the pupils at the Islamic and the comparable schools, there is no significant association: for language as well as arithmetic, it does not matter whether the pupils are at an Islamic or a comparable school.

On the basis of these findings, for the time being it is possible to conclude that pupils at Islamic schools do not do any worse than pupils at schools with a comparable socio-ethnic disadvantage. The concerns that some people feel that the pupils' performance in Dutch core subjects is poorer at Islamic schools has not been confirmed. However, the pupils at Islamic schools do not generally do any better than at the comparable schools. This means that the Islamic schools are not yet fulfilling one of their main objectives, which is to improve the educational performance of these pupils because the existing schools fall short. Time will tell whether they succeed in doing this in the future.

NOTES

- * I would like to thank the editors of the Netherlands' Journal of Social Sciences for their comments on an earlier version of this article.
1. The UK, for example, does not have a single state-funded Islamic school, nor does Germany; Belgium and France each have 1. In Denmark there are 14 and in the Netherlands 29 Islamic schools. In addition to state-funded Islamic schools, there are also some privately funded Islamic schools, which are financed by Muslim organisations. In the UK there are 30 such schools, in Germany 2 and in France 1. Islamic schools in Denmark are only partly financed by the government, and are only open to Arab and Pakistani children (with the language of instruction being Arabic, respectively Urdu), and not to Danish and other Muslim pupils (Dwyer & Meyer, 1996; Karagül, 1994; Pedersen, 1996; Wagtendonk, 1991).
 2. However, almost half the Turkish and Moroccan pupils attend privately funded and organized Koran classes after school (cf. Driessen & Haanstra, 1996b).
 3. Dutch primary schools are for 4-12-year-old children and consist of 8 forms. Compulsory education starts when the child reaches the age of 5. The first two forms are nursery classes where play occupies a central position. In the third form, formal instruction in reading, writing and arithmetic starts.

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